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WEBINAR: Scaling up bioinformatics with ABLeS, the Australian BioCommons Leadership Share

12 March 2024

Material Name	Material Type (Format)	Description	URL/Persistent Identifier
Scaling up bioinformatics with ABLeS, the Australian BioCommons Leadership Share	Recording (YouTube video)	Recording of the live webinar presentation	Available on the Australian BioCommons YouTube channel https://youtu.be/Eb0z2-yaJbY
BioCommons_ABLeS	Slides (PDF)	PDF copy of the slides presented by the BioCommons team during the webinar	Included in this Zenodo record
Mayoh_ABLeS	Slides (PDF)	PDF copy of the slides presented by Chelsea Mayoh during the webinar	Included in this Zenodo record